

Ionospheric disturbances detected by tomography for the geomagnetic storm during September 7th to 8th, 2017

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We did two cases to verify the practical effectiveness of the method, including the geomagnetic storm during August 25th to 26th, 2018 and September 7th to 8th, 2017. The following gives some results of geomagnetic storm during September 7th to 8th, 2017. Two geomagnetic storms occurred during interval of interest, we analyzed these two events by applying the improved tomography method. Figure S1 shows the first ionospheric disturbance began at 21:00 UT on September 7, then reached to its maximum at 1:00 UT on September 8 and recovered 3 hours later. Figure S2 shows the second ionospheric disturbance began at 13:00 UT on September 8, then reached to its maximum at 14:00 UT on September 8 and recovered 2 hours later.

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Figure S1 Two-dimensional distribution of ionospheric disturbance on September 7, 2017

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Figure S2 Two-dimensional distribution of ionospheric disturbance on September 8, 2017

Figure S3 depicts the tomographic results for the height and longitude profiles of ionosphere disturbances during magnetic storms. The IED changes mainly occur at a height of 100–600 km in the ionosphere, with a concentration at 300–450 km. The IED changes above 600 km are not apparent, which is related to the actual vertical distribution of IED during the quiet period. At 06:00 UT on August 26, geomagnetic activity at its peak, and IED variations are at their maximum with an increase of IED recorded at 100 and 600 km of altitude. The range of ionospheric disturbances during the geomagnetic storm is global.

Moreover, an ionospheric disturbance at 375 km height exists where the IED variation is much larger than $3 \times 10^5 \text{ el/cm}^3$. During the recovery phase of the magnetic storm, the IED changes are clearly asymmetry in both northern and southern hemispheres. The IED value in the northern hemisphere is decreasing, whereas the IED values in the southern hemisphere are continuously increasing.

Figure S3 3D variation of global ionospheric IED during magnetic storms

(a) Height profile of global IED variation during magnetic storms (b) Longitude profile of global IED variation during magnetic storms

Figure S4 displays the IED and VTEC variation at an altitude of 375 km of first storm. The IED variation reaches values from $3.7 \times 10^5 \text{ el/cm}^3$ to $9.4 \times 10^5 \text{ el/cm}^3$. An EIA is noted on the north and south sides of the magnetic equator. Figure S5 displays the IED and VTEC variation at an altitude of 375 km of second storm. The IED variation reaches values from

3.3×10^5 el/cm³ to 8.2×10^5 el/cm³. Although the ionospheric disturbance range varies over time, the main trend is east to west. The application of improved tomography method on geomagnetic storms during September 7 to 8, 2017 has a satisfactory performance on disturbance detection, which can make support to the accuracy of the improved method.

Figure S4 Variation of IED and VTEC at 375 km during magnetic storms of first storm

Figure S5 Variation of IED and VTEC at 375 km during magnetic storms of second storm